

DISCRETE ATMOSPHERIC FLUX : AXIOMATIC FRAMEWORK FOR UNIFIED LAW OF NATURE EQUILIBRIUM

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ABSTRACT

For decades, science formula is being used without proper global solution, causing it become too specialized with many correction formula. This situation become bloated and makes impossible to see the universe as one interconnected event. The science become applied derivation of nature and too far from fundamental nature. Unified Law of Nature Equilibrium (ULNE) framework is proposed to reduce the complexity of science under one simple explanation. Initially, main objective of this framework was to understand wind origin, formation and sensation. The core framework used to understand was based on Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM). Upon thorough study, it turn to gives very clear process of turbulence and the idea of entire universe is in state of equilibrium. From simple case study accidentally turn into idea of unification of various modern science field. This might sound like exaggeration, but lets dive and look the logic behind this idea. This paper explain science phenomenon as a continuous mechanical process instead of mathematical abstraction that was too complex to comprehend. There is a lot of axiom, postulate, observation and case studies to support the framework based on existing science concept. ULNE describe the law of nature, while Discrete Atmospheric Flux (DAF) is the theory that explain flux dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

I am in the process of pursuing master research study for urban pollution analysis. After reading lot of literature about urban computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and nature feedback loop, I realize the earth has natural feedback loop to maintain equilibrium. The big problem is that in most CFD cases, the air is perfect wind velocity and continuous. This become impossible to get accurate simulation data. Current CFD has two bottleneck for urban analysis, first it assume air always clean and second there is no air mixing between particulate and wind. This cause big inaccuracy, since it did not allow to predict if the wind in urban actually polluted air that flow in the same place. To overcome this is attempt to make custom CFD framework. But it is impossible to integrate as entire event is not connected. The math is everywhere, with specific error correction factor. Each of math does not talk well with each other. This lead to most fundamental question, "what is wind? where it come? how it form?". To break these ice of question, a cross-discipline understanding is very crucial. The idea is based on celestial mechanics, meteorology, physics, chemistry and others. The basis of wind formation originates for solar system, hence to understand wind, a look at the entire universe gives a new horizon.

Unified Law of Nature Equilibrium describe that nature is operate in equilibrium. If equilibrium is broken, it will undergo feedback loop, to maintain its steady state. While the main goal is to break down wind, this lead to bigger discovery and potential unification of cross-discipline science. Wind should not be treated as singular velocity object, but must be account from its individual component. This discovery might be possible to unified nuclear, electromagnet and gravity under this unified framework. Its all started with Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) which emphasize that fluid is not continuous but discrete. All matter in this world is treated as flux. When everything in this world is considered as flux, all matter must able interacted with each other without exception. The unit of flux apply from the largest nebula galaxy until macroscopic, microscopic and even in quantum theory. This framework is modelled based on LBM. This mathematical model provide direction of how the computation can be done.

In the next section, a detailed explanation of ULNE will be discussed. There are a lot of axiom, postulates, observation and case study presented to support current science phenomenon with DAF. Most of the axiom strongly challenge the current science explanation, it differ in philosophy but does not violate the calculation and existing theory. This framework provide alternative view and refinement of current model. This framework intend to explain the universe as a mechanical process rather than mathematical abstraction. This can reduce the complexity of tensor and multi dimension variable.

UNIFIED LAW OF NATURE EQUILIBRIUM

Unified Law Nature Equilibrium

In urban study, a cyclone, flash flood and volcano eruption are considered as random weather ever. Modern science giving up the idea to explain this phenomenon and developed chaos theory. However, ULNE provide justification through Discrete Atmospheric Flux (DAF) and sorption mechanics that these event is not random, but Earth self regulatory mechanism to maintain its state of equilibrium. Earth is alive and breathing, just as normal organic lives do. The purpose of weather event can be explained as follow:

- Flash flood is wet deposition process, to return the atmospheric air composition to its ideal state.
- Eruption is Earth breathing mechanism, the volcano is the valve that release excess heat accumulated underground.
- Cyclone is natural process to break the wind that violate the sorption rate.

Ideal wind follow atmospheric gas composition, which consist of 78% Nitrogen, 21% Oxygen and 1% Others. Current science always treated wind as velocity vector and pressure, but this is the biggest mystery to be broken down. Wind is not singular, hence assuming group of gas as one identity lead to major failure to understand turbulence. In this framework, the wind sensation the people feel is the flux diffusion in the atmosphere. Emphasis sorption science to understand nature of wind unlock the magic that happen in the universe. Sorption science turn wind from random and chaos into predictable diffusion of gas, which denoted as flux diffusion.

Definition

- Lattice : The container of voxel or bounding volume that seperate voxel
- Voxel : Voxel is the matter that reside within lattice
- Voxel Density : Total mass of matter present at a specific lattice node (voxel) at a given time
- Flux : The rate of diffusion of voxel between region
- Flux Overflow : The situation where flux exceeding sorption rate
- Sorption Rate – The maximum allowable sorption rate per unit area
- Sorption Limit – The maximum allowable voxel density can be contained inside lattice before undergo phase change
- Deceleration – The sorption drag of the flux upon exceeding sorption rate

AXIOM OF COMPLETENESS

Axiom I : Axiom of Universe

Postulates – The universe consist of voxel density that fill the space. Science consider space is vacuum because it lacks normal state of matter which is solid, liquid and gas. However, this framework state that outer space is not void, but contain specific voxel density. Every living being consist of flux in state of equilibrium. This flux moves the voxel across medium. When the universe not in equilibrium, it will regulate through natural feedback loop to maintain its initial state.

Observation – Flash flood and volcanic eruption is not a disaster or random event, but feedback mechanism of earth to maintain state of equilibrium.

Axiom II : Axiom of Gravity

Postulates – Gravity is an invisible spectrum that consist of flux intensity gradient. This intensity gradient pull matter toward its center. General relativity provide the mathematical prove, but the concept is very hard to digest and resulting too many theory to support its logic. This explanation provide mechanical approach of the universe in simple term.

Observation – As per general relativity, light is being bended due to spacetime. This framework agree with the process, but with different approach. Spacetime does not shrink, but light itself bended due to flux intensity gradient.

Axiom III : Axiom of Diffusion

Postulates – At microscopic level, every matter in this universe is made of voxel. This voxel moves by diffusion from high intensity region to low intensity region. The rate of diffusion of matter never exceed its respective sorption rate. This follow the chemical diffusion theory. Since the universe is made of flux, every matter that contain flux are interacting with each other. Except gravity since it is an invisible spectrum that operation in different mechanism.

Observation – This is basic science phenomena. If one drop of color put into water, the color will spread evenly over time.

Axiom IV : Axiom of Flux Conservation

Postulates – All living matter contain flux and must maintain equilibrium. There is two method of equilibrium:

- Equilibrium by Sorption Rate – If the flux diffusion rate exceed sorption rate, the matter will decelerate and shred flux.
- Equilibrium by Sorption Limit – If the flux exceed sorption limit, it will undergo phase change to reorganize allowing to contain more flux. If the flux drop beyond sorption limit, it will undergo phase change by shredding flux and release heat.

Observation – Evaporation and condensation can be described using sorption limit.

Axiom V : Axiom of Laminar Flow

Postulates – Laminar flow is possible only if one matter exist at one space. In real world scenario, this is impossible because the environment consist of multiple matter.

Observation - Light travel in space is example of near perfect laminar flow, however it still deflected under influence of gravity.

Axiom VI : Axiom of Turbulence Flow

Postulates – All flow is turbulence. Turbulence is not random or chaos, its a balance mechanism for any flux that diffusing exceeding its sorption rate. To achieve equilibrium, the matter decelerate and shred flux to keep diffuse at maximum sorption rate.

Observation – *See case study section for wind turbulence.*

Axiom VII : Axiom of Speed Of Light

Postulates – In outer space, the interaction between celestial object is about gravitational pull or flux intensity gradient. The speed of light in vacuum is not constant but it accelerating due to gravity. However, as the photon accelerating it hit the sorption rate, which limiting to constant speed of c . To overcome the speed limit, the photon require burst energy or the voxel path along photon direction need to be cleared.

Observation – As the photon accelerated, it shred flux while moving forward to maintain state of equilibrium. This shred flux contributed to solar wind.

Axiom VIII : Axiom of Time Conservation

Postulates – Time is not part of dimension, but it is periodic variable that moves alongside the space. Time does not contain flux to be described as part of universe dimension. Time is conserve but the information transfer is lagging. The idea of time dilation only come up to fit the Theory of General Relativity.

Observation – N/A, purely hypothesis.

Axiom IX : Axiom of Singularity

Postulates – Earth is not singular but made on interaction of three body Earth-Sun-Moon. Traditionally the impact of sun and moon gravity is considered negligible. However, the impact of sun and moon during diurnal not to be underestimated, the force is huge. This become more critical in era of precision and microscopic.

Observation – Tidal wave increase up to 18m during diurnal.

Axiom X : Axiom of Wind

Postulates – Wind is not just a single air with velocity or pressure, but a lattice that made up of respective voxel density of atmospheric gas. The wind sensation that people feel is flux diffusion. Since wind is not fundamental, it should be broken down to more basic component. This is crucial to understand complex phenomena such as turbulence and weather event.

Observation – Wind consist of 78% Nitrogen, 21% Oxygen and 1% Others.

Axiom XI : Axiom of State of Matter

Postulates – There is four state of matter which is solid, liquid, gas and plasma. However, by Unified Law of Nature Equilibrium, gas state is colorless. Gas only can obtain color when it has enough density to trap light spectrum. Plasma is divided into two category which is weak plasma and strong plasma. Weak plasma is partial ionize, which can be seen as fire or flare. While strong plasma if fully ionize matter which cause strong ignition. Dividing plasma into two category significant in explaining phase change and flux distribution of voxel or lattice.

Observation – Halogen gas has different color when exposed to different light spectrum.

Axiom XII : Axiom of Nuclear Explosion

Postulates – There is no nuclear fusion or fission. It is basis of the same principle at but at different scale. Nuclear explosion is simply an intensity mismatch that can be describe in two term:

- Micro-Macro : Light matter diffuse through heavy matter entering plasma state
- Macro-Micro : Heavy matter diffuse through light matter in plasma state

Observation – Pure hydrogen explosion is smaller scale than uranium explosion. By Axiom of State of Matter, any gas that exceed sorption limit turned into plasma, either weak plasma or strong plasma.

Axiom XIII : Axiom of Solid

Postulates – All living object is not static. The flux is constantly moving at low sorption rate even in solid form. A solid form can never be deformed. It must undergo phase change to reorganise and change lattice structure.

Observation – *See case study section for metal forming.*

Axiom XIV : Axiom of Decay

Postulates – Only dead will decay and decompose. Dead only occur when matter lost flux. Since the lowest state of matter is solid, all dead matter is in solid state. Dead matter does not follow state of matter. In chemical science, it is assume this matter receive heat of decomposition and turned to ash. But to ULNE logic, heat only increase rate of decay for dead matter because it does not have flux to undergo phase change.

Observation – Wood is not an element but an organic component. Wood does not has flux or alive, so it does not follow state of matter. The core wood component is not part of periodic table. Since it dead, it will decay. Same applied to metal oxide, it cannot be used as raw materials as it dead solid matter.

METHODOLOGY

Wind Formation Process

1. Assume bulk gas at open ocean is at steady state. The flux is in equilibrium.
2. Evaporation introduce vertical diffusion of vapor. This increase intensity of bulk gas.
3. The sun (photon) is reflected among the bulk gas voxel. This increase flux intensity.
4. The bulk gas now exceeding the sorption limit. To maintain its equilibrium, the bulk gas need to shred flux.
5. The shredded flux is drifted by earth rotation, providing a circulation path.
6. Ssun and moon gravity cause wind tides.

Method of Measuring Wind Flux

To effectively measure the wind flux, the sampling can be done at atlantic to pacific ocean boundary. This is the most ideal place because:

- The air in assume clean. The wind composition same as ideal atmospheric composition.
- Less noise. The only radiation from water is evaporation, reducing uncertainty.
- The atlantic and pacific ocean has different water density, hence having evaporation at different rate. This provide starting point to estimate flux diffusion.

Mathematical Model

- Lattice Boltzmann Method – Main framework
- Monte Carlo Ray Tracing – Photon transfer
- Mie Scattering – Photon flux interaction in air
- Sorption Science – Chemical diffusion mechanics and fundamental
- Phase Equilibria – Equilibrium and phase change

CASE STUDY

Time Dilation Paradox

General Relativity assume spacetime is bending and time is part of dimension. This view lead to our believes that times in space much slower than on earth. However, according to Axiom of Universe, all living being in this world contain flux that constantly seeking for equilibrium. The photon is a flux that moving along the outer space voxel density. As the photon moves near three body, the earth gravity bend the photon toward its flux intensity gradient, causing slightly long trajectory. By this logic, spacetime is not bended, but information transfer is lagging. This strongly supported by Axiom of Gravity and Axiom of Time. This view is agree with Einstein idea that light is bended, but this explanation implement mechanical process instead if mathematical abstraction that require additional logic such as tensor and 4Dimension.

Metal Forming

Metal forming is a study under materials science, one of the hardest subject in engineering. Metal bending usually occur at low sorption rate. Metal is a lattice container in solid form. A bending machine exert the additional flux to the metal, cause the voxel slide and accumulate at one point, until hitting the sorption limit. According to Axiom of Flux Conservation by Sorption Limit, the voxel will undergo phase change when exceeding sorption limit, by reorganize to maintain state of equilibrium. This can be represent as semi-liquid state. When the process complete, the machine release the flux. Hence metal the flux also decrease, and the voxel reorganize until density beyond sorption limit and solidifying. The metal need to maintain equilibrium under standard atmospheric condition. Hence it has shred flux and release heat. This process also emphasis that, a lattice structure cannot we formed in solid state, it require phase change to reorganize as per Axiom of Solid.

Breaking Glass

Unlike metal, breaking glass does not release heat. This phenomena can be explain using Axiom of Flux Conservation by Sorption Rate. Glass has very low sorption rate. The glass break by excess sorption rate, before it ever exceeding the sorption limit. In the event where glass collide with hard surface, the flux is being diffuse above glass sorption rate. This situation is unstable, require glass to regulate its condition to the point of equilibrium. To overcome excess sorption rate, the voxel require to shred some flux, cause the glass to broken into pieces. However as it never exceed sorption limit, there is no phase change or heat generated.

Reynold Experiment

Reynold experiment dated back during 1883, he tested a fluid flow in a pipe, then and a little drop of color. The observation is that the flow initially laminar, until fully developed region it become turbulence. As stated is Axiom of Laminar Flow, laminar flow is impossible when two different matter occupied within same space. The voxel will of red colored fluid will always diffuse toward clear water. However since the event occur at microscopic, its not noticeable by naked eye and percieve as laminar. In Axiom of Turbulence, the water represent heavy matter while the color represent light matter. A light matter cannot diffuse through heavy matter freely without deceleration. To move further, the red color used Bernuolli's Principle, drifted by the water flux flux diffusion. At initial state, the red colored fluid flux is below sorption rate, allowing smooth flow. In an open loop flow, the velocity is increase from point A to point B. The fully developed region is the region where the flux of red colored fluid flux exceeding its sorption rate. Its analogy same as people run an hitting the wall, forced to stop. Hence to overcome the limit and maintain its equilibrium, it decelerate and shredding some flux. The shredded flux contain flux lower than sorption rate. Accorting to kinetic theory, a matter diffuse from high density region to low density region. The decelerate flux diffuse toward the shredded flux that has lost the path. Red colored fluid now losing its original path causing the phenomenon we interpret as turbulence. In Axiom on Diffusion, it is state that flux diffusion never occur at rate exceeding the sorption rate. The turbulence observed is due to mechanism of red colored fluid to maintain flux below its sorption rate.

Wind Turbulence

This is the most mysterious phenomena in the universe that science cant describe. I simply denoted as chaos and random weather event. This is because we always consider wind as one entity. First we need to understand formation of wind. One example is during rainy day. The cloud is from vapour form reduced to liquid form. According to Axiom of Flux Conservation, phase change require the matter to shred flux and release heat. The flux that being drift by earth rotation is the wind that our science describe. The turbulence, however ever occur within at smaller scale. Ideal wind composition consist of 78% Nitrogen, 21% Oxygen an 4% Other Gas. Each component has different diffusion rate. Lets take example for at least the wind contain one heavy matter and one light matter. As discussed in reynold experiment, the light matter is drifted by heavy matter and maintaining laminar flow at initial state. What comes next is different, unlike reynold experiment that study on small scale and limited velocity, the flux can recover its equilibrium to diffuse forward. But in real scenario, the flux diffusion is more harsh. For the light matter, the only matter that moves forward is that follow sorption rate, while the shredded flux actually bouce backward. This phenomenon is critical for shredded flux to restore equilibrium. As the shredded flux moves in opposite direction, the deceleration zone is strong enough to return it below sorption rate. Once it stable, it being drifted again by the incoming wind, following original direction. This is why wind turbulence is a swirl, it is a phenomena that component wind has to maintain its equilibrium by not violating its sorption rate, as per Axiom of Diffusion.

Wet Deposition

At humid country, flash flood often occur during the highest intensity of urban heat island. In most cases, we consider this as random event or disaster. But as per Axiom of Universe, the universe must stay in state of equilibrium. Flash flood is not random, but the earth mechanism to achieve equilibrium. Ideal air consist of 78% Nitrogen, 21% Oxygen and 4% Other Gas. When the composition change, heavy gas reside within urban canopy, forcing the vapour flux to diffuse upward at highest rate. The limit of vapour flux vertical is just beneath litosphere. Lithosphere is denser than vapour, acting as lattice boundary for the vapour voxel. Faster flux diffusion means faster voxel accumulation beneath lithosphere. Because it is the limit of vapour, the region become dense. Incoming vapor flux undergo deceleration, losing it flux. As the flux drop below sorption limit, the vapour will undergo phase change to maintain equilibrium. Vapour turning liquid start merging with each other forming heavier liquid. Because urban heat island vapour usually hotter, this means more flux need to be shredded and more heat released to transform into liquid form. As a result, the wind produced is harsher and the rain also intense. The rain swept all the dirty particle in the air to the ground. This process call wet deposition, its not only reduce the pollution in the air, but return the atmospheric air to the equilibrium state.

The Black Hole

Axiom of Speed of Light stated that light diffuse at constant rate because it is the equilibrium state to pass the voxel intensity of outer space. On the other hand, blackhole is a heavy matter with very high voxel and flux intensity. This means the sorption rate of blackhole is high, thus allow diffusion of photon. This is the case intensity mismatch. Upon entering blackhole, the photon exceed sorption limit, causing phase change and enter excitation state. This is case of explosion as stated in Axiom of Explosion. Excitation state is not stable, photon shed some flux to overcome deceleration inside blackhole and maintain equilibrium, the speed now far below c , losing the identity of light. On earth, when a car crash at high speed and hitting a wall, it will bounce back while the wall crush. The photon simply follow the same mechanics. On the blackhole part, this high intensity flux sorption between two matter cause slightly turbulence flow at the corner of this large body. The flux leftover by photon now become solar wind.

Chromatic Dispersion

Chromatic dispersion is an event where we see the blue sky. It can be described using Axiom of State of Matter. All gas should exist in colorless state, this same to earth atmospheric gas. However since the earth atmosphere is heavy and dense, it can trapped spectrum of light. The most intense light is blue color. At dawn, the photon intensity decrease, causing different spectrum of light trapped which is orange. At night, the is no light passes the sky is clear at night, allowing people to see object from outer space.

High Temperature Hydrogen Attack

Hydrogen attack is the hardest problem in materials science, its hard to detect the failure because the damage is microscopic.. Hydrogen attack often result in internal structure failure, methane formation, embrittlement and leakage. This problem usually occur at high temperature and pressure. To describe this, we must follow Axiom of Flux Conservation. Hydrogen is the most simplest and lightest matter in the universe. That means it has lowest sorption rate and lowest sorption limit. The metal tank is the solid lattice container. Upon pressurized, the hydrogen flux sorption rate toward metal tank increase. A collision means increase of flux, the hydrogen atom exceed sorption rate or even the sorption limit. If the hydrogen reach sorption limit of gas, it will undergo phase change which is becoming plasma. However the state of plasma is weak plasma. The hydrogen at plasma state is unstable, hence to achieve equilibrium, it shread flux and release heat, turning gaseous state again. This micro-explosion cause micro-flux excitation on the steel tank lattice. To overcome micro-flux excitation, the steel tank shred energy, release the lightest matter which is Carbon for the lattice structure. This event lead to micro-crack and formation of methane. The issue is not detectable by naked eye or common measuring tool as it is microscopic. Over time it cause bigger crack and eventually leakage. During leaking, there is high pressure release of hydrogen in gaseous state. This is a case in Axiom of Explosion of micro-macro explosion. Since hydrogen is light, it has low sorption rate, so it cannot penetrate much further without significant deceleration. The strong deceleration cause increase in flux exceeding sorption limit. Hence the hydrogen turn into plasma state, which is the ignition. Despite hydrogen ignition, there is also secondary flare, which due to oxygen compression in the air. Flare also consider a weak plasma state, because it is phase change from gas to another state. To return to equilibrium, both hydrogen and oxygen shred flux and release heat. The explosion scale is small because hydrogen flux cannot penetrate further in heavy air.

FUTURE APPLICATION

- Particle Physics
- Meteorology
- Cosmology
- Space Exploration
- Solar CSP Plant
- Urban Particle Dispersion Simulation
- Marine Engineering Ballast Management
- Rust Propagation on Wind Turbine

CONCLUSION

ULNE framework might unified science of 2000 years of study under one broad term. We observe that any earth event is the sorption mechanics, where every matter need to maintain equilibrium. By treating all motion as flux diffusion, we only has one unit to concern, measure of flux. This simplified math very well. Newton was first to unified physics, second unification is electromagnetism by Maxwell. Third unification is Einstein. This might be forth model of unification, by re-identifying wind. Wind is not fundamental force, it is a group of bulk gas. In this era of microscopic and computational, treating gas and singular and continuous lead to major drawback. In the past the industry rush to use science which is theoretically incomplete. They introduce lot of correction algorithm or formula that leads to bloat. In ULNE framework, science is always same no matter we are on earth or on space. Else our description of science might be inaccurate. By treating wind as flux, we are bridging the classical and quantum mechanics. This might be the key to unite the fundamental force, or mostly known as unified field theory. To conclude, this study of flux dynamics is just to expose the indentity of wind, but I found that it us able to describe cross-discipline science. ULNE framework able to eliminate various argument of phenomena and magic of nature with just flux dynamic. Feel free to discuss, prove or contradict this theoretical framework.

LIMITATION

The main objective of this frame is to understand the nature of wind. The explanation of turbulence is that this framework excellent. The other nature event is derived to because the framework itself originates from cross-disciplines, hence viewing it from wide perspective seems to make some connection. However, for other event other than turbulence, this hypotheses does not to account the real chemical reaction or gas mixing that may cause inaccuracy.